

Handout for source-based 3D
reconstruction
on the example of
the former synagogue in Speyer
in 1250

Table of content

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Methodology	3
3. Assumptions outline	3
4. Sources collection	4
4.1 Photos.....	4
4.2. Research reports.....	5
3.3. Analogies.....	6
3.4. Other reconstruction projects.....	7
3.5. Organisation of source materials.....	7
3. Structure	8
4. Modelling	9
5. Uncertainty	10
6. Documentation	11
7. Publication.....	12
Appendix	13

1. Introduction

The handout presents the methodology developed for the case study of the reconstruction of the former synagogue in Speyer in 1250 AD within the research project “DFG-Viewer 3D – Infrastruktur für digitale 3D-Rekonstruktionen”¹ and is a topic of interest of the Arbeitsgruppe Digitale Rekonstruktion (AG Digitale Rekonstruktion)². The aim of this paper is to test scientific approach for documentation and publication of the source-based digital reconstruction.

2. Methodology

The proposed methodology for the digital reconstruction treats the 3D model as the result of scientific work, where all the choices that have been made during the process are accurately documented. This allows the preservation of the information behind the model and its evaluation. The final publication in the online 3D repository is thus vital for sharing the results and giving access to the scientific content carried by the model.

The different steps of the proposed methodology will be explained in the next chapters. They mainly include:

- The identification of the object;
- The collection of sources;
- Their classification according to their nature (photos in the location, archaeological reports and texts directly related to the synagogue, analogies with other buildings...);
- The creation of the structure of the model (identification of the hierarchy of semantical elements);
- The modelling phase;
- The documentation of the reconstructed elements;
- The publication of the results.

3. Assumptions outline

The first step is to draw up an overview of the assumptions for the reconstruction model of the object. Prepared description should contains information about objects name, location, function and presents the object during the phase, which will be reconstructed. It should also covers the outline of the requirements, scope of development or level of detail applied to the 3D model. A good starting point for object description may be to check websites such as Wikipedia³ or Wikidata⁴.

Description made by Irene Cazzaro for the Speyer Synagogue in 1250 AD is as follows:

“The object of concern is the medieval synagogue of Speyer (in today’s Germany), whose remains are still visible at the Judenhof, near the Speyer Cathedral. It is one of the best-preserved synagogues of the 12th century in Europe. Consecrated in 1104, the Romanesque building was then restored approximately in 1200 – again in Romanesque style – after a fire. In the second half of the 13th century it was renovated in Gothic style and a women’s synagogue was built attached to it. The synagogue was the centre of the Jewish life until the 16th century, when, after several persecutions, only a few Jews still lived in Speyer. Our digital reconstruction takes into account the synagogue in 1250, thus during the second Romanesque construction phase. Some remains dating back to that time are still visible: the external walls, for instance, are still partially standing and in the western facade we can see

¹ <http://dfg-viewer.de/>, last accessed 24.03.2022

² <https://digitale-rekonstruktion.info/>, last accessed 12.04.2022

³ <https://www.wikipedia.org/>, last accessed 12.03.2022

⁴ <https://www.wikidata.org/>, last accessed 12.03.2022

two windows that are copies of the original Romanesque ones preserved in the Judenhof museum. It is assumed that at that time the walls, according to some small traces found on them, were covered with plaster. A portal was situated on the northern wall, whereas on the eastern wall the remains of an arch – part of the Aron Hakodesh – are still visible. There are no traces of the roof.”

Outline of requirements for the same model made by Igor Bajena is as follows:

“The building should be placed in the middle of a flat fragment of terrain with dimensions of 25 x 25 m and a depth of 3.0 m and the depth of the foundations should be about 1.5 m. Some elements of interior equipment are excluded from the study. Modellers were required to model an ideal version of the building, where geometry is based on the right angle, without any deformation. The main objective was to test the methodology and technical solutions rather than to imitate the illusion of realism.”

The description should also consider the purpose of the model and what information it provides. It is also important to include characteristic information about the model, especially in the case when the same topic is reconstructed in several versions by different people.

4. Sources collection

Sources collection is fundamental for digital reconstruction. It can consist of many steps and can often evolve during the process enriching our reconstruction with new findings. Activities in this stage include photographic documentation of the location, visits to museums dedicated to the subject of reconstruction, searching for plans in archives, collecting articles, books and archaeological findings, and trying to find analogies, which can fill in the gaps caused by the lack of sources regarding particular elements of the building.

Other reconstruction projects carried out on the same object can also be an important element of the process. However, reconstruction projects are always marked by a certain level of hypothesis (uncertainty) and they should not be considered as the main source of the new research – rather they should be used to test new hypotheses. The assumptions made at the start of each project can affect its level of detail and development. This can mean that the same building, when reconstructed in different projects and with different constraints, can look very different.

4.1 Photos

In the case of the synagogue reconstruction project, it was possible to successfully locate and prepare photographic documentation of both the remains of the building and the exhibits of the local museum (Fig. 1). A map with the location of each image has been prepared to make it easier for modellers to use the photographic resources (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 Photo of the remains of the former synagogue in north-western direction (©Irene Cazzaro) and Physical remains detached from the original structure exposed in the museum (©Irene Cazzaro)

Fig. 2 Location of the pictures taken in the location of the former Jewish quarter in Speyer. The numbers correspond to the numbering of the files in the source folder containing the photos (©Igor Bajena).

4.2. Research reports

The sources have been enriched with a bibliographical research, which was conducted both in libraries and online. Most of the sources are articles published after the excavations in the early 2000s; one of the descriptions was published in 1759. Of particular importance in the textual studies are the sketches that show the hypotheses that have been put forward, which can serve as a starting point for further research (Fig. 3). Archaeological excavations have made it possible to date individual parts of the building remains. This has enabled us to determine precisely which fragments have survived from the period covered by our reconstruction (Fig. 4).

b) vor 1230

Abb. 52 Rekonstruktion der Synagoge von Oden. Die Haarlينien geben den Umfang der erhaltenen Bausubstanz wieder. Hinsichtlich weiterer Fensteröffnungen sind keine verlässlichen Angaben möglich. Quelle: Beschreibung von Georg Litzel (wie Anm. 6) und Unterlagen Günther Stein (wie Anm. 40); Entwurf/Zeichnung: Verfasser.

Fig. 3 Drawings showing possible reconstruction of the eastern elevation by Christopher Engels, 2001

Abb. 9: Speyer, Bauphasenkartierung der Ostwand der Synagoge

Fig. 4 Drawing illustrating different construction phases of the building on the elevation of the synagogue

3.3. Analogies

Due to the lack of sources for some elements of the building, analogies with structures from the same historical period or with similar constructive systems were found (Fig. 5).

Abb. 21: Worms, Portal der Synagoge während des Wiederaufbaus 1959/61

Abb. 3: Vergleichende Zusammenstellung von Synagogen des 12./13. Jahrhunderts

Fig. 5 Portal of the Worms Synagogue and Medieval synagogues in Erfurt, Rufach, Nördlingen, Miltenberg, Maribor, Korneuburg, Tulln.

3.4. Other reconstruction projects

For the former synagogue in Speyer two other reconstruction projects have already been carried out. The first of them was done in 2004 by Architectura Virtualis in cooperation with the University of Darmstadt, for the exhibition „Europas Juden im Mittelalter“ in Speyer, where the goal was to obtain a simulation illustrating the history of the building with its various Romanesque and Gothic building phases. The second one was carried out by the Institute of Architecture at Mainz University of Applied Sciences (AI MAINZ) in cooperation with the General Directorate for Cultural Heritage of Rhineland-Palatinate in 2021 for the exhibition “DIGITAL URBAN HISTORY LAB” at Mainz State Museum. In this project the goal was to obtain a model for 3D printing, which has completely different requirements and levels of detail. A comparison of the final product of both projects is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 On the left: rendering of the reconstructed synagogue in Speyer in Romanesque phase – view of the western and northern wall (©Architectura Virtualis, 2004)); on the right: model of the reconstructed synagogue in Speyer in 1250 prepared for animation – view of the western and northern wall (©AI Mainz, 2021,).

3.5. Organisation of source materials

The organisation of source materials is extremely important from a documentation point of view. The lack of logical arrangement of collected sources may lead to their omission in the reconstruction process.

In the presented example, each source type has its own file name in the internal source directory, which allows referring to the file name of the sources in the documentation process. The file naming system is as follows:

- Books: book_nr
- Research articles: article_nr
- Descriptions: text_nr
- Photos of items from the location: photo_location_nr
- Reconstruction rendering: reconstruction_nr_rendering_nr
- 3D models: reconstruction_nr_model_nr
- Archaeological reports: report_nr
- Researchers drawings: drawing_nr
- Analogies: analogy_nr
- Starting materials and guidelines: guideline_nr

In case a source is divided into a number of parts, we need to add “_nr of part” at the end. Example: Part 2 of the text source 1 will be named as “text_01_02”.

All sources should be then listed in a table, for instance in an Excel file (in our case we created different Word files for each type of source as in Fig. 7).

Fig. 7 The separate files with the list of sources – divided according to the type of source – inside the “Attachments” folder

3. Structure

In order to carry out the scientific documentation, the structure (hierarchy) of the building must be distinguished according to the project assumptions. A controlled vocabulary should be used when creating the division, an example of which is Art & Architecture Thesaurus® Online developed by the Getty Research Institute⁵.

In the example shown below (Fig. 8), a three-stage hierarchy was chosen. Its implementation in various 3D programs was one of the elements of the case study. Adding the third element of the hierarchy – type – was necessary due to the appearance of elements classified into one group in different variants (type a, type b, etc.). The implementation of the selected building hierarchy with the identification of the individual building elements is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8 Structure of identified elements based on the Art & Architecture Thesaurus® Online (©Igor Bajena)

⁵ <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

CATEGORIES

- Enclosing Elements
- Surface Elements
- Spanning Elements
- Supporting and Resisting Elements
- Openings
- Religious Building Fixtures

ELEMENTS/TYPES

- | | | |
|------------|-------------|------------------|
| 1a Walls a | 5b Beams b | 9 Doorway |
| 1b Walls b | 5c Beams c | 10 Aron Hakodesh |
| 2a Roof a | 6 Cornice | 11 Foundation |
| 2b Roof b | 7 Plinth | |
| 3 Floor | 8a Window a | |
| 4 Ceiling | 8b Window b | |
| 5a Beams a | 8c Window c | |

Fig. 9 Applying different structural categories to the building and identification of the types of structural elements (©Igor Bajena)

4. Modelling

From the beginning modellers should consider the level of detail (geometry), texturing (materials) and context (surroundings), and whether there are any elements that should be excluded from the .

For Speyer synagogue, it has been determined which elements will not be included in the study (Fig. 10). It was also recommended to use prepared ready-made textures to reduce modelling time and make it easier to spot differences when exporting files from different programmes.

Fig. 10 Elements excluded from the reconstruction (©Igor Bajena)

5. Uncertainty

In order to declare to which extent the collected documents allow an accurate reconstruction, we propose the use of an uncertainty scale. In our example, the uncertainty level of an element is not attributed according to the nature of the sources that are used (photographs, drawings, written descriptions...), but rather according to the physical (on the object) or mental (on the sources) work we have to do to reconstruct an element, according to this classification:

- survey / physical analysis of the remains;
- analysis of sources directly related to the object (texts, drawings, photos, existing parts similar to missing ones);
- analogies with similar buildings;
- hypotheses not based on sources.

In the light of these considerations, a colour scale has been proposed starting from the following one (Fig. 11):

UNCERTAINTY DEGREE

Fig. 11 Uncertainty scale according to the physical or mental operations (@Irene Cazzaro)

Uncertainty visualization also depends on the level of detail (geometry) of the model: in the case of the Speyer synagogue, a level of uncertainty should be assigned to each element that composes the structure of the model as seen in chapter 4. The only exception is the external wall, which is only partially standing: in this case, a distinction is proposed between the existing part, reconstructed by survey (from the documented still existing remains) and the missing part, reconstructed by deduction (assuming that it is similar to the still existing one).

Both a colour and a value are associated to each uncertainty level:

- **4- blue** stands for the still existing parts;
- **3- green** for the elements reconstructed by deduction, because they should be similar to the existing ones or they are mentioned in documents directly referring to the building;
- **2- yellow** for the elements reconstructed by analogy starting from other structures of the same historical period;
- **1- red** for the elements reconstructed by hypothesis, because there are no available

- sources for them;
- **o- black**, if necessary, for the elements that are not taken into consideration for the uncertainty estimation. This could be the case of the 25x25 m fragment of terrain where the model of the synagogue is situated.

If possible, the colour should be implemented in the visualisation of the model (Fig. 12), the numerical value in the attributes of each element. As this proposal is under evaluation, the adequacy of the scale will be tested while modelling, thus some adjustments may be necessary at later stages.

Fig. 12 Application of the uncertainty scale to the exterior (on the left) and interior (on the right) of the synagogue provided in Rhinoceros: for each uncertainty level a different layer – with a colour according to Fig. 11 – was created (@Irene Cazzaro).

6. Documentation

To stress the scientific nature of the reconstruction, a documentation of the reconstruction process has to be delivered with the 3D model. During the reconstruction process, the decisions and steps (process) should be documented (captured) by screenshots. The documentation has to be prepared for all identified objects during the semantic division of the object (see chapter 3 – structure). This documentation should include a list of sources used for the reconstruction of a specific element, an estimation of the level of uncertainty and a short text argumentation.

A template for documentation is provided with this handout ready to use. Completed examples of this template can be seen below (Fig. 13):

Wall type 1			Portal		
Reconstructed object					
Used sources	report_05.jpg				
	photo_location_01.jpg				
Argumentation and evaluation of the uncertainty	This is the part of the wall that we can still see		Argumentation and evaluation of the uncertainty	We do not have traces of the portal of the Speyer synagogue, but we can reconstruct it by analogy e.g. with the portal of the medieval synagogue in Worms	
		04-still existing			03-analogy

Fig. 13 Example of already filled out templates for the documentation of the reconstruction process (©Irene Cazzaro)

7. Publication

The final step is the web-based publication of the results, enabling the access to the scientific 3D model. For this purpose, a 3D repository has been developed (<https://3d-repository.hs-mainz.de/>). The publication of the 3D model requires a field-based entry of information about the model (metadata) and the upload of 3D data set. Current version of metadata scheme is still under development and is attached in Appendix of this paper. .

To publish your model in the above-mentioned repository, please contact Igor Bajena via e-mail (igorpiotr.bajena@unibo.it). The access to the repository will be granted.

In case of any question regarding to:

a) 3D modelling assumptions, structure of the building, documentation, publication, sources in the form of other reconstructions – contact Igor Bajena: igorpiotr.bajena@unibo.it

b) history of the building, sources in form of photos, drawings and texts, uncertainty scale and its application to the model – contact Irene Cazzaro: irene.cazzaro2@unibo.it

Appendix

Proposal of metadata scheme – under development.

